

**The Geriatric Patient under the Frame of Modern Medical
Methodologism: Expert Discourses, Practical Applications, and
Philosophical Implications [1]**

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**Гериатричният пациент в рамките на съвременния медицински
методологизъм: експертни дискурси, практически приложения и
философски импликации**

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Abstract: *The paper examines the question of how the patient is framed as an object of diagnostic and medical knowledge, focusing on the phenomenon of ageing. The issue is addressed through a synthetic approach, combining the paradigms of medical anthropology, phenomenological-hermeneutics, and discursive analysis of normative texts. This perspective attempts to draw critical attention to the incorporation of the so-called medical methodologism and modern scientism, classically considered to be value-neutral and universally applicable to medical practices, regarding various forms of physical and mental suffering.*

The figure of the geriatric patient opens the possibility for a critical look at 1) the symbolic monopoly over the understanding and the interpretation of the human condition which the official medical discourses may be exercising explicitly and implicitly, and 2) the historical dynamism of the renegotiations of the boundaries of categories such as health, norm, and pathology.

Keywords: ageing, geriatric patient, medical methodologism, medical anthropology, philosophy of medicine

Резюме: *Статията изследва въпроса как пациентът бива рамкиран като обект на диагностично и медицинско познание, поставяйки фокус върху феномена на стареенето. Проблемът е разгледан чрез синтетичен подход, съчетаващ парадигмите на медицинската антропология, феноменологично-херменевтичния метод и дискурсивния анализ на нормативните текстове. Избраният подстъп се опитва да привлече критично внимание към възприемането на т.нар. медицински методологизъм и на модерния сциентизъм, които класически са считани за ценностно неутрални и универсално приложими към медицинските практики по отношение на различни форми на физическо и психическо страдание.*

Фигурата на гериатричния пациент отваря възможността за критически поглед към 1) символичния монопол върху разбирането и тълкуването на човешкото състояние, който официалните медицински дискурси могат да упражняват

експлицитно и имплицитно, и 2) историческия динамизъм на преговарянето на границите на категории като здраве, норма и патология.

Ключови думи: *стареене, гериатричен пациент, медицински методологизъм, медицинска антропология, философия на медицината*

The aim of this paper is to pose the question of how the figure of the patient is framed as *an object of diagnostic knowledge and medical interventions*, focusing on the phenomenon of aging. The starting points for this investigation are sources such as the volumes of the “International Classification of Diseases” (ICD) and the “Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders” (DSM). Developed by the World Health Organization and the American Psychiatric Association respectively, over the course of the second part of the 20th century both classifiers have acquired the status and function of standardized international tools applicable in a wide variety of medical diagnostic practices and/or as basic reference points when discussing issues like mental health, nosology of pathologies, etc. Such bodies of work reflect and further shape the ever-developing course of the medical science and its normative tendencies. They are designed both for clinical purposes and health management, as they square a key role in insurance practices, health policy making, etc. Furthermore, one of the primary goals of these volumes is to advance scientific knowledge. They introduce not only the task of classification but also that of statistical analysis as fundamental to scientific generalization, referring to groups of cases and in a clear and unified terminology (cf. WHO, 1957).

The dynamics of medicalization, but also of re-medicalization and de-medicalization, testify both to the implicit understanding that the aspects falling within their frameworks (should or shouldn't) belong to the field of medicine, and that their redefinitions are not simply based on objective scientific discoveries, facts, revolutions, etc., but are also a form of consensus, the validity of which has its historical, social, cultural, professional, economic, etc. grounds (cf. Charland, 2013).

A space for critique of these processes can be opened by the hermeneutic paradigm which emerged during the XX century and has continued to develop to the present day. Not unlike medical anthropology for example, this perspective attempts to draw attention to the incorporation of the so-called *medical methodologism* and modern scientism, which are classically thought of as value-neutral and universally applicable to medical practices and the diverse forms of physical and mental suffering they are aimed at.

One of the most prominent commentators and critics of the processes of dehumanization of modern medicine is undoubtedly Hans-Georg Gadamer. His texts

repeatedly turn to the modern biomedical sciences, which, according to him, seem to be bracketing the question of the patient's experience, while at the same time obscuring the key mediating role of the practitioner, be it clinician or therapist.

For Gadamer, the technologized and unpersonal approach adopted by medical knowledge, according to him, is rooted in the *ideal of certainty* (Gadamer, 2015), coming from the epistemological attitudes of the seventeenth-century natural sciences, which place all understanding under the frame of the 'measurable' and 'provable', subjecting human existence and the bodily experience to different forms of objectification. His approach attempts to illuminate the foundations of a so-called modern medical ethos that finds its origins in the incorporation of a scientism that can be described as "the cool and dispassionate attitude of the physician, one that tends to regard the body as an object of measurement, is not value-neutral; it is, rather, a purposive and value-laden practice or *way of life* embedded in a life-world, one that identifies detachment and objectivity as the default standpoint for genuine knowledge" (Aho, 2017:118). In this context, Gadamer's ideas are not only relevant to the question of understanding and making intelligible the experience of aging and old age as a dialogue, as shared task between oneself and the relevant others, but also to the investigation of the dynamics of the medicalization and the symbolic stakes, underling the professional medical field.

Notes on the Biomedicalization of Old Age

Between the 1930s and 1950s, when the study of the biological properties of aging became a prominent problem, there was practically no epistemic consensus regarding the functional and evolutionary essence of the processes and phenomena in question, which hindered their (scientific) definition. For example, the very framing of the processes at stake are object of debate – as whether they should be considered as the complete course of development over the lifespan, i.e. from birth to death, or aging had to be distinguished from senescence, the latter of which is understood as a 'downswing of life'. In addition to this, the problem of the "degrees" of pathologization of aging remained a key issue, raising the question of whether this is an entirely morbid phenomenon, or there should be isolated categories of normal or 'pure' and pathological aging. These in turn imply the possible construction of typical and atypical clinical pictures of the so-called older population. This and many other problematizations of the geriatric medical discourse are indicative of the oscillation of the thresholds of (a)normality of old age and aging. They however, are not

isolated, but interact with the overall historical (scientific, institutional, social, etc.) context in which the boundaries of *health* and *illness* are drawn and redrawn.

As noted by numerous researchers of the history of the institutionalization of geriatrics and gerontology, the attempts to overcome these obstacles also reflect on the approaches through which at that time this field tackles its subject of research and praxis, gradually adapting the biomedical model of illness and disease, in which aging is framed and “defined as a matter of ‘biomedical’ interest” (Moreira, Palladio, 2009, p. 350).

Along with a large part of the other hard sciences and humanities, these fields are strongly influenced by the economic and demographic changes occurring in modern and late modern societies, characterized by the increase in life expectancy and the aging of the population – a phenomenon that requires the rethinking of key moments in the policymaking and the overall social attunement. In addition, there is a need to restructure the leading “biomedical-clinical orientation [that] is premised on an acute-care model of medicine” (Estes, Binney, 1989, p. 590) towards the incorporation of approaches adequate to the treatment of chronic diseases and comorbid conditions – phenomena which, by presumption, are often associated precisely with advancing age and imply the so-called *coordination of bench and bedside* – a situation that oscillates between the (self)-management of one’s own health and the different modes of professional and institutional (medical) care.

This situation suggests trans-social dynamic transformations that affect post-war societies in many ways. In the seminal text “The Biomedicalization of Aging: Dangers and Dilemmas,” (1989) Carroll Estes and Elizabeth Binney comment on two major aspects of the biomedicalization of aging as: “(1) the social construction of aging as a medical problem (thinking of aging in terms of a medical problem) and (2) the praxis (or practice) of aging as a medical problem (behaviors and policies growing out of thinking of aging as a medical problem)” (ibid, p. 587). According to the authors, the dominant framing of old age through the prism of the medical and clinical paradigm in the second half of the 20th century interprets and presents this phenomenon as a linear and stable process of decline, tied to negative categories such as ‘weakness’, ‘loss of control’, ‘dependence’, ‘degeneration’ and ‘death’.

In 1981 for example, the Bulgarian journal “Sotsialno delo” published a long-standing discussion about the test establishment of separate geriatric service units in Bulgaria. Among other things, these entries commented on the specifics of the geriatric patients and their particular, yet ambivalent character, situation and expectations, requiring additional attention,

understanding and delicacy on the part of the medical internist. Although these were seen as an affirmative quality of the latter, the possibility of working exclusively with the ‘contingent of the elderly population’ was considered as having negative professional and personal results: “The patient sees the familiar face of his doctor, and that already has its psychotherapeutic effect. But the doctor is also a person with all the complexity of the psyche. Isn’t there a danger that the geriatrician will get wearied by the severe human suffering in its unaesthetic and hopelessness and reach an indifferent and formal attitude to his duty?” (Vlahliyska, 1981: 22).

This discourse focuses on given illnesses as a sum of individual organic pathologies (such as dementia, for example) – an emphasis that permeates the social fabric, settling into everyday interpretations of these experiences through clinical categories. The biomedicalization of aging can be traced through the interweaving of the coordinate system of scientific-professional-policy-mundane understanding and representation of this phenomenon.

Last but not least, the very expectations of the individuals (as suffering subjects) in their position as patients, as well as the ‘doctor-patient’ relationship, are remodeled through the medicalizing prism of these symbolic orders. As stated by Gadamer „[i]n the case of transient illnesses and ‘eliminable’ pain we have learnt to regard them as no longer important. Consequently, modern medicine has principally seen itself confronted by chronic illnesses and the different challenges they present. For here it is a question of tending the ill, which also requires attending to their mental and emotional well-being” (Gadamer, 2015: 76).

Already in 1989, the cited paper raised the question of the objectification of the clinical patient-experience, based on the situation in which “the primary focus is on illness as an individual problem with individual causes and individual solutions. For elderly persons labeled by virtue of their age as diseased and disabled, individualism may contribute to a “blame the victim” mentality as well as to social control through the medical management of their problems (e.g., through drugs or institutionalization), since such decisions are usually made in individual structural situations of vastly unequal power relations between physician and patient” (Estes, Binney, 1989, p. 588).

Undoubtedly, these problems touch upon the particular question of what it means to be an (elderly) patient, especially in the situation of long term and/or palliative care, where one’s life-history may be paralleled by a trajectory of survived, suffered and/or still-lived-with diseases and medical treatments.

A quarter of a century later, Sharon Kaufman, Janet Shim, and Ann Russ return to the topic, but this time through the perspective of routinizing and normalizing an ever-widening range of medical procedures and pushing back the age limits of their eligibility. For them, although these practices offer the possibility of maintaining life expectancy, in hindsight they can lead to the deprivation of the individual's *agency*, narrowing the field of choice and decision-making regarding one's treatment, at the same time making the modern (aging) patient a figure of *responsibilization*. As they may be perceived as both naturally deprived of life in health, and at the same time having the medical opportunities (which also imply different modes of obligation) for a well-informed healthy life.

Old Age and Aging in the Diagnostic Scope

To illustrate another facet of the dynamic changes in the framing of aging as a medical phenomenon I will continue with a brief account on its place in the preliminary phase of the diagnostics, where it signifies a certain oscillation between the categories of 'health' and 'pathology'. Below I will use examples from the classifiers mentioned above, as on the one hand, they illuminate different aspects of the issue, and on the other – their development is parallel and mutually informed, although not completely symphonized, providing sense of international continuity between differentiated healthcare systems. The historical trajectory of these texts, along with the institutions and organizations behind them, is crucial for understanding the processes of normative framing of the categories of 'health' and 'pathology'. However, this investigation will be limited to the scope of the current topic [2].

Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders

A case in point regarding these dynamic processes is DSM. Its first two iterations (*DSM-I*, published in 1952, and *DSM-II*, in 1968) followed a paradigm based heavily on psychoanalytic theory and psychotherapy, largely depending on the so-called *talking cure* methodology. The widespread and popularization of this type of therapeutic practice, however, led to a strong parcelization of the approach, which lacked both a general theoretical consensus and one regarding the applied techniques, which as a result undermined the legitimacy of the psychiatric field. This led to the need to introduce generally valid diagnostic criteria and treatment protocols, the fruit of which was the publication of *DSM-III*, initiated by the American Psychiatric Association in 1980. In addition – it is in this third version of the manual that the systematic work on maintaining the continuity between its nomenclature and that of ICD's and the overall international standardization of diagnostic

criteria and practices begins. The exchange between the two classificational systems is also lined by the active participation of the APA in the ICD task force, regarding the class of mental disorders.

It is for this reason that the leading emphasis in this edition falls on the scientific rigor that relies on the idea that the handbook “like Newton, it [DSM-III – D.N.] makes no hypotheses (*hypothesis non fingo*) about the underlying processes at the root of the disorder. It offers only a “descriptive approach [and] attempts to be neutral with respect to theories of etiology” (cf. APA 1994, p. xvii–xviii). This approach is continued and strengthened in subsequent revisions. It has been heavily criticized as legitimizing a decontextualized and mechanistic attitude towards the human condition, focusing on a single, apparently ever-expanding, set of symptoms to be accommodated in diagnoses whose criteria have been pre-established.

Keeping this context in sight, the figure of the geriatric patient offers many opportunities for analysis. As the possibility for 1) a critical look at the *symbolic monopoly* over the understanding (not only as scientific, but also everyday knowledge) and the interpretation of the human condition which the official medical discourses are exercising explicitly and implicitly, but also 2) at the historical dynamism of the renegotiations of the boundaries of categories such as *health*, *norm* and *pathology*, and 3) at the very ways by which the problem of the (ab)normality is approached.

The question of the place of the phenomenon of old age and aging in the context of modern and late modern medicine from this point of view is particularly interesting. Especially bearing in mind the special, niche or even marginal status of geriatrics and gerontology as a specific unit of medical science and clinical practices in the post-war period.

A short inquiry of the contents of the *DSM* series shows that the first two editions (1952; 1968) include diagnostic systematization by age in the tables of various types of medical information about the patient (that are also administrative documents) [3]. In the earliest editions age is arranged by the logic of even time slices, and later on – by life-periods, concluding with the category “late life”. At the same time categories such as ‘old’ (as if in ‘old age’), for example, are almost absent when linking specific conditions with a given stage of life.

As the later revisions became more and more descriptive that changes [4], and in addition to that the inclusion of certain age markers – for example “age 65 years and older” “after age 60 years” and etc. starts to increase alongside with the frequency at which they are

used in relation to the framing of sets of symptoms, diagnoses and conditions. The most common forms in the later revisions are using the word “elderly”, both as a noun and as an adjective for the naming of different clusters of addressees – “elderly persons”, “elderly males” and “elderly females”. The age-related categorizations as ‘older individuals’, ‘older males’, ‘older females’ and ‘older population’ also are frequently used and expanding (cf. APA, 2005, p. 141; APA, 2013, p. 200).

Similarly, the notion of *aging*, began to be addressed predominantly after the third revision of DSM, and not only as a part of the course of development over the lifespan, but also as an organic process – “brain aging”, “skin aging” etc. and as a *normative categorization* – “normal aging”, “normative aging process”, although it’s marked as explicitly unstable. The sporadic appearance of the aforementioned phrases “geriatric patients”, “geriatric populations” and “geriatric individuals” in the latest edition of DSM and its text revision may be understood as a farther step towards categorization with a clear emphasis on the individual’s role/position as patient i.e., as someone objectified by the medical gaze. Meanwhile such categories operate also on the level of homogenization, as older people are addressed as a general segment of the population. In addition to that, the term “gerontology”, which denotes the field that is aimed at the study of the broader aspects of the phenomenon of aging, is absolutely absent from these texts.

It seems like the later revisions became more explicitly aware of the theme of age, but at the same time it should be asked how this new sensitivity can be understood in the wider context of medicalization? How should we analyze these subtle changes in the discursive framing of the phenomenon in question, as both part of the dynamic scientific field with its predispositions and presumptions, and as a category that contains certain axiological connotations in the *Zeitgeist*?

It is interesting to note that for example, the term ‘late life’ appears in the earlier editions mainly in the context of the so-called *Transient Situational Disturbances* as a matter of *the problems of physiological, situational, and environmental readjustment* that may be caused by non-pathogenic situation – a condition that is otherwise hard for diagnostic “taming” via checklist of meet criteria. This implies a rather contextual as opposed to an organic form of pathogenesis of the so-called personality disturbance (or disorder) that can occur in any stage of life but its specifics are age-defined. And “Late life” is one of these stages.

With DSM-III the focus shifts from transitivity to adjustment as the condition is redefined by the umbrella term “Adjustment Disorder” – an additional diagnosis in “which the disturbance, by definition, is a reaction to psychosocial stress” (APA, 1987, p. xxiii). This, on a discursive level, may be interpreted as a change in the patient’s role and activity – as if they *must* adapt, that is, their (un)ability to do so, not their overall life-situation is the defining feature here. As we can see after the text revision of DSM-III this type of disturbances begun to be clustered not primarily by age, but by the seemingly main “disturbance”, that the individuals are experiencing.

It can be debated that within its periodical updating, *DSM* addresses old age and aging both as a cause for and as a factor in different pathologies, in this case – in the shape of the mental disorders.

International Classification of Diseases

Since 1948 the World Health Organization has been the main publishing force behind the *International Classification of Diseases* as “a global, multilingual catalogue of known human diseases, medical conditions, and mental health disorders, to standardize disease diagnosis” (Rabheru, Byles, Kalache, 2022, p. e457). Its roots can be traced back to 19th century. Its initial statistical purposes reflect the need for systems to classify causes of death. The most famous of which is the Bertillon Classification. The same served as a basis for the international classification. Here ‘old age’ was regarded under the separate class *XII. Diseases of old age* (cf. Rosenberg, Hoyert, 2011).

The deliberate organized efforts for internationally applicable systematization of such a kind were established in 1893 by the International Statistical Institute (ISI), that later culminated in the publication of the first *International List of Causes of Death* in 1900, where ‘Old age’ was listed under the number 167 [5]. During the first half of the 20th century the list underwent several readjustments, introducing more deployed systems for coding and nomenclatures. In the span of the next revisions ‘Old age’ is part of the detailed nomenclatures regarding both the ‘statistics of the sick’ and the ‘statistic of the death’. In the second revision (1909) listed under that title again is only ‘Senility’ and it is stated that it was used for civil and military hospital records. The tabular list of synonyms and the related diseases reads:

“Senile debility. Old age. Cachexia (old persons). Marasmus or exhaustion: senile. Senile dementia.” (DCL, 1910, p. 63)

Nevertheless, the category of ‘senile’, is also prominently included in other diseases, such as *senile decay*, as it marks the age-specific type of pathology or condition, that may also have other causes and/or sub-types.

The next revision (1920) linked 9 diseases and/or causes of death to ‘old age’, namely *atrophy, cachexia, debility, dementia, exhaustion, gangrene, imbecility, marasmus, and paralysis*. However, an explicit note was made that terms like “Old age” and “Senility” are indefinite and undesirable, as they were: “Too often used for deaths of elderly persons who succumbed to a definite disease.” (see DC, 1924, p. 38). In that respect, if possible, a more precise use of the nomenclature was desired, as it was needed for statistical, etc. purposes. The list of conditions under the latter title included more than 35 entries. While *ICD-2* defined 5 basic age groups, the last of which ‘Over 60 years’, in *ICD-3* the usual age-specified demarcation that prescribe given condition/cause of death to the category of ‘old age’ is (70y+). The upcoming revisions present even more strictly divided age groups as their accuracy is key for the classification of the cause of death under a given title.

ICD-4 (1929) changes some of the titles of its classification, making the class head “Senility” instead of “Old age”. The latter is used in the detailed coding list. This section acquires more subdivisions that are defined by the presence of pathology in correlation with chronological age: (a) *With senile dementia*, (b) *Without senile dementia (70 years and over)*, (c) *Premature senility (55 years and under 70 years)*, and (d) *No cause given, no doctor in attendance (70 years and over)* (cf. DBS, 1933). This may be understood as a symptom of the de-medicalization of old age *per se*, at the expense of its case-specific morbid course of development. Nevertheless, it also should be interpreted in the broader contextual sense of biomedicalization of health and pathology. It illustrates a trajectory toward an attunement of the classificational (and diagnostic) scope – an explication of clearly defined and distinctive pathological states, events and conditions. In that case ‘old age’, although still a key factor for the development of such, isn’t seen as a sufficient (diagnostic) inference.

The next decennial revision of the international classification (1938) used the title “Senility”, including again subdivisions indicating the presence or absence of dementia. In some of the accompanying materials the title is joint – “Senility, Old age”, and it is still noted that ‘old age’ or ‘senility’ shouldn’t be stated as a cause of death if a definite disease is present (cf. DBS 1946, p. 51), being considered as the primary condition or event causing the death. The applicability of this category is restricted to the individuals aged 65 years and over. The overall direction taken in the preparation and the implementation of this version is

towards comparability and “the growing necessity for a corresponding list of diseases to meet the statistical needs of widely differing organizations, such as health insurance organizations, hospitals, military medical services, health administrations, and similar agencies” (WHO, 1957, p. xiv).

This notion is even more strongly reflected in the sixth revision of *ICD* (1948). It is also the first one published under the responsibility of the WHO. This edition reflects the evolution in scope – from primarily a classification of causes of death to a comprehensive system for classifying both mortality and morbidity. That is also reflected in the change of its full title, being *International Statistical Classification of Diseases, Injuries and Causes of Death*. This meant that the more sophisticated coding, which introduced third and fourth digits and three new lists of tabulations, could be applied to the notion of multicausality, but also to a broader range of non-fatal diseases, injuries, and other health-related conditions. In that respect it could serve not only for vital statistics, but also as a basis for common diagnostic language. The new revision merged the titles “Senility” and “Ill-defined Conditions” in a new section named “Symptoms, Senility and Ill-Defined Conditions”. From the description of the class, it is clear that the emphasis on conditions and symptoms that aren’t assigned to any of the previous’ categories as they aren’t yet well-defined, point to more than one disease or systems, or could not be assigned to a final diagnosis. The states in this section are considered as “not otherwise specified”, as of “unknown etiology”, or as “transient” (cf. WHO, 1949). The inclusion of “Senility” of that list is indicative. The subdivision contains symptoms and conditions such as ‘Nervousness and weakness’, ‘Headache’, ‘Unqualified uremia’. Notions likewise ‘old age’ and ‘senile’ are still in use, but a significant majority of them is included as typological details in other sections, “Mental, Psychoneurotic, and Personality Disorders”, “Diseases of the Nervous System and Sense Organs”, “Diseases of the Circulatory System”, “Diseases of the Respiratory System”, etc. In that way ‘old age’ or ‘senility’ became more of an age-defined circumstance or characteristic of certain biologically and medically well-defined pathological states. The term ‘senile’ for example, could be attached to any of the atrophic organs or systems of the human body.

ICD-7 (1955) followed the same logic, as it was seen as a period for the principal adoption and the expansion of the international multi-institutional usage of the coding system, framed by the previous revision. It described its systematization as eclectic taxonomic philosophy, the hierarchical principal of which was based “on frequency, importance, and clarity of characterization of the condition” (WHO, 1957, p. xxviii).

“Senility” keeps its position as a subdivision of the same class. The tabular list of “Senility and ill-defined diseases” has six three-digit codes. It is important to note that otherwise, ‘old age’ is rarely included in the detailed coding, while ‘senile’ is still in use. It is stated that in the presence of a cause under another section, the condition of ‘Senility’ should modify the code, but it should be primary classified under the latter (ibid, p. 364).

These adjustments mark the transition of the medically elusive conditions of ‘old age’ that couldn’t be defined as solid diagnosis to the so-called “garbage code” (see Zhavoronkov Bhullar, 2015) i.e. classification of the cause of death (for a death certificate for example) or disease under a code that is considered as non-specific and vague, or as obscuring another underlying cause and in that way – leading to distortion in the mortality or morbidity statistics. The parallelization of these processes of biological aging with those of unspecified symptoms and conditions illustrates the progress (and the expectation) in the sphere of medical science and in the gerontological investigations as a biomedical discipline – to define pathological phenomena through aging as a clearly determined set of morbidities or failing systems. At the same time, it puts under titles such as ‘senility’ and ‘old age’ these phenomena that it renders as yet ‘untamed’.

The next revision (1965) introduced major changes to the classification’s indexing system, based on the current scientific knowledge and the requirements for its practical implementation in different settings. A result of that was the complete drop out of the notion of “Senility” in the title of the section, which became “Symptoms and Ill-defined Conditions”. Again, regarding the conditions included of this division an extended note with examples was included, discussing the modification rules for more useful tabulation of the mortality data. The phenomena in question were referred as “manifestation of the aging or disease process” (WHO, 1967, p. 419), as their etiological roots weren’t sufficiently clarified. Terms like ‘senescence’ and ‘old age’, appear as descriptive units. The notion of “Senility” lost its position of a subtitle. It headed the tabulation ‘Senility without mention or psychosis’ (in the subsection “Ill defined diseases”) and was featured in ‘Senile and pre-senile dementia’ (in the section “Mental disorders”) in the main text, ‘senile’ still being the most frequent attribute, used in other classes.

ICD-9 (1975) continued the efforts of adopting its classification for hospital and clinical use and for medical care programs, which required an even more detailed classification approach. In order to achieve that, it was recommended that “the mortality orientation of the classification and assumptions of etiology be discontinued and that multiple

conditions be coded separately rather than in combination categories in the classification” (cf. Rosenberg, Hoyert, 2011: 20). This led to the decision a number of conditions to be coded in two ways – in respect to their etiology (for mortality tabulations) as a primary code, and to their manifestation – as a secondary one. The class that housed ‘senility-related’ phenomena changed its title again, becoming “Symptoms, Signs and Ill-defined Conditions” (WHO, 1977). The divisions were reorganized by the degree of their diagnostic clarity, while the three-digit category “Senility without mention of psychosis” was included in the last sub-category “Ill-defined and unknown causes of morbidity and mortality”, alongside with “Sudden death, cause unknown” and “Other ill-defined and unknown causes of morbidity and mortality”, underlying the unclarity of such classification. The sections accommodating “Mental disorders” received narrative descriptions similarly to these introduced in *DSM*. Here ‘old age’ is present as a stage of life, having effect on certain mental disorders or condition such as ‘senile dementia’ and ‘cognitive or personality change of other type’.

The tenth revision of the classification (1989) introduced significant structural changes, improving its suitability in order “to serve a wide variety of needs for mortality and health-care data” (WHO, 2016, p. 14). This was also confirmed by amending the title *International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems*. The new list initiated an alphanumeric coding scheme that presented more complicated, but dynamic way of coding. The revisited text addressed ‘old age’ both as a period of human’s life-course and a cause of particular age-related diseases (e.g. cachexia), disorders (e.g. dementia) or tendencies (e.g. ‘tendency to fall’). The three-digit tabulation ‘Senility’ was included in the renamed chapter ‘Symptoms, signs and abnormal clinical and laboratory findings not elsewhere classified’ under the title “General symptoms and signs”. It consisted of ‘old age’, ‘senescence’, ‘senile asthenia’ and ‘senile debility’. The notion of ‘age-related’ conditions and morbidities is also frequently used in the detailed coding index. In this context, the discursive cluster related to ‘old age’, as a broad non-medical term, is even more explicitly regarded as a phenomenon that should be the subject of biomedical investigations and interventions. However, it is not yet scientifically ‘tamed’ enough to be fixed in an unequivocal classificational unit and/or diagnosis, leaving little room for the notion of ‘natural causes’.

But the most controversial point in the modern development of ICD, regarding the processes of medicalization of ‘old age’ came with the preparatory work for the latest revision of the international classification – *ICD-11* (endorsed in 2019 and effective from

2022). The discussion was ignited by a draft proposal initiating two related changes. The first one was the inclusion of an additional extension code in the causality section of the classification. It defined the notion ‘aging-related’ as “caused by pathological processes which persistently lead to the loss of organism’s adaptation and progress in older ages” (cf. Rabheru, Byles, Kalache, 2022, p. e457). The second modification planned the replacing of “Senility” with “Old age” as a code, still in the diagnostic section of ‘symptoms, signs, or clinical findings not elsewhere classified’, being the center of resistance. It was initiated by the notion that over the past few decades the term ‘senility’ gained significant negative and pejorative connotations, going beyond its clinical use. Nevertheless, although the term ‘old age’ was constantly present in the previous iterations of the classification and the two were frequently used as synonyms, the official labeling of the latter as a diagnosis (as an act of institution) was seen by global organizations and activists in the field as a further step towards pathologization of aging, or as a prerequisite for ageism, being deemed as a disease or abnormality. While WHO identified the phenomenon as a ‘normal human attribute’ and not as a disease, but rather a ‘disease risk factor’ [6] and a major issue of public health, the application of the broad, commonly used term, alluded to a negative framing of chronological age in general. This was an effect unintended by the WHO’s ICD-11 committee.

This led to the suggestion of three replacements: “(1) “senescence,” as a biological term, refers to the condition or process of deterioration with age. Cells undergo senescence throughout the lifecourse, but the process increases with aging; (2) “ageing associated decline in intrinsic capacity” is a term that recognises the biological, physiological, and psychological processes of aging and their effect on a person’s intrinsic capacity; and (3) “frailty” is a measure of increased risk for developing an age-associated syndrome that stems from reduced reserve across multiple physiological systems and decreased resilience to daily stressors” (ibid, p. e458).

Arguments were made from both sides, using deferent strategies for legitimation. Those who welcomed the changes, relied exclusively on biomedical and/or practical approach. For example, in the first case arguing that the current clinical findings lead to the conclusion that aging ‘fits’ *ICD* criteria for disease (cf. Khaltourina, Matveyevb, Alekseev, Cortesed, Ioviță, 2020), and in the second – that its classification as such will open more possibilities for clinical trials via increase funding, thus progressing the knowledge of this processes and improving older people’s health; it will “result in new approaches and business models for addressing aging as a treatable condition, which will lead to both economic and

healthcare benefits for all stakeholders” (Zhavoronkov, Bhullar, 2015, p. 1). In addition to that, it would raise the *symbolic capital* of medicine and gerontology as a competent provider of treatment, against a close, but nevertheless concurrent field – the wellness market. And last but not least, it will extend the *symbolic power* of “the medical practitioners to convince patients to pursue healthier lifestyles and prescribe medication, even in cases where patients are comfortable with the condition” (ibid, p. 5) – an argument that illustrates the problem of patient’s *agency and autonomy*, regarding life-related decision-making and the asymmetry in the doctor-patient relationship.

The opposers also rely on expert discourses, underling that ‘old age’ is essentially a blanket term, having limited possibilities both for individual diagnosis and for population health programs (see cf. Rabheru, Byles, Kalache, 2022, p. e457), as aging is considered to consist of heterogenous processes with “substantial interindividual variability”. But their concerns gravitated explicitly around the possible socio-cultural and moral outcomes, and the existential implications of such form of categorization of that segment of the population, and of the overall way-of-being.

As a result ‘Old age’ was withdrawn as a head category and replaced with the more nuanced ‘aging associated decline in intrinsic capacity’, shifting the focus from the pathologization of the state to a cluster of morbidities, related to the (negative) effects of aging as a process [7]. Changes were adopted also for the causality code of aging-related conditions, substituting the term “pathological” with “biological”, having more neutral connotations (WHO, 2022). These formulations, nevertheless imply a case of deviation from the norm of health as an ideal optimum.

Conclusion

The observations and conclusions made so far illustrate the dynamic processes that underline the role of the old age-related categorization in respect to the medical field and patient-care. In this context although the topic of ‘old age’ and ‘aging’ is consistently at present at the margins of the diagnostical scope, its presumptive demedicalization and remedicalization is heterogeneous. Its reliability and feasibility as a classificational and diagnostical object shift through different iterations – as a ‘mortality and morbidity cause’, as a ‘condition’, as an ‘ill-defined symptom’, as a ‘disease’, as a ‘normal process, having pathological forms’, etc., the connotations of which permeate and are permeated by its framing not only as a biomedical property, but also in existential sense.

Notes

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[2] It is crucial to note that this examination is focused primarily upon the official or normative framing of these phenomena and alongside with that – their presentation as exemplary for the related fields on a discursive level, and not upon their actual practical implementation, which is a key issue requiring separate attention.

[3] The following exposition does not present an exhaustive content or discourse analysis of all the revisions, but intends to sketch some key tendencies.

[4] *DSM-III* for example acknowledges the conduction of studies concerning “disorders in old age”.

[5] Retrieved from: <http://www.wolfbane.com/icd/index.html>, 05.02.2024

[6] See *The Lancet Diabetes & Endocrinology. Editorial. Opening the door to treating ageing as a disease*, volume 6, issue 8, p587, August 2018, available at [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landia/article/PIIS2213-8587\(18\)30214-6/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/landia/article/PIIS2213-8587(18)30214-6/fulltext),

09.05.2024

[7] The latest revision provides detailed extension codes of for the time of life in which the onset is occurring. They identify the age period between 25 and 64 as ‘Adult’, between 65 and 84 as ‘Early Geriatric’, and over 85 to the end of life as ‘Late Geriatric’, this being the only referring to the notion. This once again illustrates how these stages of life are framed via medical discourse.

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